

Impact of Foreign Aid on Primary Education Amid Corruption in Pakistan

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Abstract: *The main objective of this study is to analyze the impact of foreign aid on the educational outcomes of primary level in presence of corruption. Besides, the study also strives to throw a discussion on the situation of education in Sindh and the role of corruption in education. The study uses time series data over the span of 1995-2012. It is concluded on basis of the empirical results that the ODA disbursed to Pakistan has positive (insignificant) effect on the Gross Enrollment Rate of primary education. However, it has negative impact on the enrollment rates when corruption is interacted. Moreover, the condition of education in Sindh is vulnerable. The study also finds various forms of corruption in education at political, administrative and school levels which are both monetary as well as non-monetary in nature.*

Key Words: *Foreign Aid, Millennium goals, Primary Education, Corruption*

1.0 Introduction

Foreign Aid is an important contributor in the social and economic development of a country particularly referring to the underdeveloped and developing countries. The green revolution in agriculture sector, vaccination of childhood diseases and elimination of river blindness are remarkable outcomes which resulted from efficient and effective use of foreign aid in several sectors in the developing countries (Anwar & Aman 2010). From the fact that developing countries own limited resources of their own; most of these countries look for assistance in the form of foreign aid. To improve the development of various sectors of the developing countries the rich countries of the world in nineteenth century determined to help poorer countries and decided to provide funds in the form of grants, loans as well as technical assistance for budgetary support (Anwar, 2014). At various conferences (Jomtien Conference, 1990; Dakar Education Conference 2000; Millennium Summit 2000) the international community set some targets as well as made commitments to provide necessary funding to the under developed and developing countries that undertook those targets for achieving the goals of these conferences (Malik). The United Nations' Millennium Summit in 2000 designed eight Millennium Development Goals (MDGs) that are targeted to be achieved by 2015. Among these, the second goal

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is to achieve Universal Primary Education (UPE). Under this goal, target 2A states that all children including girls and boys can complete a full course of primary schooling by 2015, which may be measured by enrollment in primary education and completion of primary education.

Pakistan is one of the signatories of international conventions on education. Those include Jomtien Education for All in 1990, Dakar Framework of Action (April 2000) and United Nation's joint declaration on education called "Millennium Development Goals" (MDGs in September 2000). Being a signatory of Education for All program of UNESCO, Pakistan⁵ is determined to achieve universal enrollment⁶ in primary education by 2015. Government issued national education policy (NEP) documents in 1970, 1972, 1992, 1998 and 2009. Moreover, in order to ensure transparency and accountability in making the best, efficient and effective use of foreign aid, from time to time government has introduced various measures such as Education Sector Reform Program, National Plan of Action (NPA), National Education Assessment System (NEAS), School Management Committees (SMCs), Social Action Programs (SAPs). The Government of Pakistan has been adopting various strategies for education sector aimed at improvement of the existing schools, working on education quality improvement, bringing increase in enrollment, ensuring better access to education and broadening of the primary education system. National Education Policy 2009 concentrated on various issues including the access to education, bringing disparity (equality) and quality of education at all levels. It targets to achieve hundred percent enrollment rates, hundred percent completion/survival rates and ninety percent literacy rates.

Foreign aid⁷ to Pakistan gets immense publicity of playing an important role in the education sector due to various reasons i.e., low revenue generation capacity of country and small allocation of resources to the education sector which result into low educational outcomes. The education sector of Pakistan has been going through crisis like other developing countries. Miserably, Pakistan has been spending only two percent of its GDP on education sector (Sattar). Due to low spending by government in education sector creates shortage of funds which is then fulfilled by the foreign donors (aid agencies) for various purposes, mainly for the improvement and development of social sectors. Despite a massive increase in the foreign aid by the developed⁸ countries and other international sources, the

⁵ The constitution of Pakistan under Article 37(b) states "*The state shall remove illiteracy and provide free and compulsory secondary education within minimum possible period*".

⁶ In 2001 Education Sector Reform (ESR) was also one of the policy which comprises of seven goals including significantly increasing the national literacy rate; providing universal education with increased completion rates and reduced gender disparity and improving education quality through curriculum reform, teacher training and assessment reform. The purpose of ESR was "*Education for All*".

⁷ By late 1950s, Pakistan became aid recipient; however, with the introduction of every five year plan and the rapid increase in industrialization, the volume of this aid kept increasing. Initially, this aid was offered on easy terms and conditions but as time passed, Pakistan faced difficulties in getting aid.

⁸ It was by 19th century that developed countries and Multilateral Organizations started funding the developing and underdeveloped countries.

results of major outcomes in education sector have been low and also the effectiveness of foreign aid has been under question. Based on unproductive public consumption, corruption⁹, inefficiencies, bureaucratic failure and poor development of institutions, the experts have argued that foreign aid is just wastage of resources in the developing countries. Besides many other problems associated with foreign aid, it is also argued that due to the bad and corrupt governments in developing countries, a great portion of the foreign aid goes wasted (Anwar, 2014; Khan, 2007)¹⁰.

1.1 Education and its importance

Education is like an investment into human capital. Millennium Project of UNDP identifies education as “A vehicle of nation-building through which a nation’s shared interpretation of history and cultural values are reproduced across generations”. Through development of productive and skilled labor force by infusing in them knowledge, skills and creative strength, education serves the purpose of achieving economic growth at national level. Education is closely associated with making better earning returns. MDGs rank education and health as the driving forces for development. Particularly, the development in human resources and sustainability of social and economic growth are closely associated with education.

It is quite imperative to note that education is one of the basic human rights as well as one of the main drivers for economic and human development. As a social observation education brings awareness among people, it enlightens their perceptions towards literally everything in life. Through education, they become able to understand health issues and can address them promptly. If a society is educated, it is likely to build a healthy nation; healthy nation in terms of physical, mental and social health. Foreign Aid helps government in increasing the spending in education sector; as a result of which it builds a more productive workforce and hence, a productive and stronger economy. A productive workforce, in return, helps in curbing economic problems like poverty, hunger etc, hence contributing in the overall development of the economy. (Anwar & Khalid, 2011).

1.2 Problem Statement

In view of above discussion it is evident that foreign aid is necessary for development purposes. The available literature supports the important role played by foreign aid in various sectors but it also suggests that there is little significant move in the educational outcomes due to foreign aid. The literature in recent years also identifies the destructive role of corruption in education. Moreover, after the

⁹ The World Bank and other multilateral institutions refer to corruption as “*The abuse of public office for private gain*”. It also opines that corruption, corrupt practices and corrupt behavior vary from one country to another.

¹⁰ Then the increase in corruption by the public officials became much noticeable by the time of Independence in 1947. The prevalence of corruption in any country is treated as a threat to its economic, political and social development. Among the monetary costs of corruption, World Bank reports a total of 1 trillion Dollars (\$1000 billion) worldwide corruption every year. From various studies (World Bank, 2001).

question of aid effectiveness came under debate (World Bank, 1998), several researchers directed their work into finding the effectiveness of foreign aid, while others questioned the hindrances created in education sector due to corruption. Considering, the available studies it is evident that the prevalence of corruption in a country hinders the outcomes of education. This research paper, therefore, jointly attempts to study educational outcomes, aid effectiveness and corruption. It studies the impact of foreign aid on primary education of Pakistan but in prevalence of corruption in the country.

1.3 Objectives

The main objectives of this research are a mix of descriptive and quantitative/empirical type. First two objectives are quantitative in nature whereas the last objective is qualitative in character. This research study would strive to achieve following objectives:

- To analyze the relationship among foreign aid, education and corruption in case of Pakistan
- To measure the impact of foreign aid on the education of Pakistan amid corruption

2.0 Literature review

This section gives the review of the literature related to the effectiveness of the foreign aid with relation to education. Many researchers i.e., Michaelova (2004), Anwar and Khalid (2011), Anwar & Aman (2010), Mahmood et al, (2010), Asiedu & Nadwa (2007), Michaelowa & Weber (2007), Khalid (2012) and Ahmed, (2001) found that foreign aid positively affect education in developing countries. Some of these researchers have found insignificant impact of aid on education. Michaelowa (2004) studied the impact of aid on education sector and found positive but insignificant impact of aid on the enrollment of primary education and suggested that donor as well as the recipient governments to increase spending in this sector. Anwar and Khalid, (2011) by using ARDL approach studied the effectiveness of foreign aid in the light of Millennium Development Goals on the education sector using ARDL approach on the data for the period 1973-2008. They found that the primary school enrollment in Pakistan has significantly been increased due to foreign aid both in long as well as in short run. The empirical study of Anwar and Aman (2010) suggested positive and statistically significant relationship between foreign aid and education sector and the aid disbursement with the literacy rate of the Pakistan building a basic model in order to make this study more convenient to linkages of educational outcomes with triggering catalysts foreign aid. Mahmood et al, (2010) found negative relationship between foreign aid and primary school enrollment. Baldacci, Asiedu and Nadwa (2007) examined the impact of foreign aid on education considering heterogeneous nature of aid and the heterogeneity of aid recipient countries. They concluded that there is positive impact of aid on higher education growth in case of middle income countries. Further, they have concluded negative impact when foreign aid was spent on primary and secondary education. Michaelowa and

Weber (2007) found positive relationship of aid in education sector and the enrollment in primary schools. This study argued that the institutional and political background of the countries receiving aid also matters. Moreover, the impact of aid turned to be negative in case of some countries. Michaelowa et al (2007) worked on foreign aid and education of schools and they found out that there is positive and significant relationship among aid and school education and its enrollment. Michaelowa (2004) conducted a dynamic panel analysis on 120 low and lower-middle income countries by using the control variables related to the national education expenditure, national education system and some measures of governance of the aid-recipient countries. Researcher concluded that total aid to education sector has a positive but insignificant impact on the primary enrollment rate and primary completion rate.

Many researchers have attempted to find out the role of foreign aid in the development of Pakistan, as the country has been receiving foreign aid for its development programs right from its independence as a separate state. Literature on effectiveness of foreign aid to Pakistan, suggests that aid has helped in increasing growth in the country whereas the effects of aid on education pose mixed results.

According to Myint (2000) there are many forms of corruption in Pakistan like political and financial corruption, nepotism and misuse of power. Furthermore he concluded that poor governance in Pakistan is behind all this corruption in the country. Discussing the reasons behind corruption in education sector Transparency International (2007) states that poorly maintained classrooms, overcrowding in classrooms, teacher absenteeism, shortage of textbooks and educational supplies and such other problems as main reasons. The corruption thus done can be traced to political, administrative and school level actors. Samad (2008) identifies corruption as a complex study which involves historical, political, cultural and socio-economic factors. She has further argued that socio-economic and political system of a country is greatly hindered of corruption. Anwar (2014) in her study empirically examined the determinants of aid effectiveness using panel econometric technique for the period 1990-2011 in Asian countries. The study concluded positive effect of corruption and other variables on the official development assistance (ODA)¹¹. Myint (2000) identified corruption as a major hindrance in way of development and growth process of any country. Chapman (2002) studied in particular how the small level corruption in education sector affects it. Poisson (2010) states that the research on corruption in education triggered as a result of OECD's convention on combating bribery of foreign public officials in international business transactions in 1999 and United Nations' Convention against Corruption (UNCAC) in 2003. From the recognition of damaging impacts of corruption and its adverse effects on the social and economic costs. Abdiweli and Isse (2003) conducted a study on determinants of economic corruption. They have found positive and significant relation of foreign

¹¹ Official Development Assistance (ODA), a sub-category of foreign aid is the total official aid extended to various sectors for development purposes. World Bank defines ODA as the flows which are extended to the countries listed with Development Assistance Committee (DAC) as recipients of aid (Hanifa Anwar, 2014).

aid and size of government. The aid extended to social sectors helps a great deal in bringing improvements and developments in the social sector. Moreover, some studies have concentrated on finding out the effectiveness of foreign aid on education or educational outcomes; while others have focused on corruption in education. However, there still is need of finding out the role that corruption plays in creating hurdles in way of educational outcomes when the education sector is being funded with both the inland funds (resources) as well as the foreign funds.

2.1 Framework

2.1.1 Model

Based on the description of variables above, the basic model of this study is presented in form of a diagram as below:

2.1.2 Variables' Diagram

2.2 Hypothesis

Keeping in view the background study, available literature and the variables used, it is hypothesized that:

There is positive impact of foreign aid on education; however, the effectiveness of its impact is affected (negatively) by prevalence of corruption.

3.0 Methodology

The study implies three main variables as discussed below:

Education: in this study, education is used as dependent variable. As its provision and quality is dependent on other variables like availability of resources within country and the funds provided in support.

Foreign Aid: The study uses foreign aid as Independent variable. This is because the supply of foreign aid helps bring improvements in various sectors. For this study, the impact of foreign aid is to be studied on education sector of Pakistan.

Corruption: The third variable to be used in this study will be corruption as a control variable.

3.1 Econometric Model

The data is analyzed based on a functional approach. Following Michaelowa and Weber (2007), Anwar & Anam (2010) and Anwar & Khalid (2011); a functional

form showing dependent variable education (represented as Edu-outcomes) independent variable foreign aid (represented with ForAID), and control variable Corruption (represented as CorpI being the corruption index) is shown in following equation:

$$\mathbf{Edu (outcomes) = ForAID + CorpI \dots\dots (i)}$$

The educational outcomes may be measured either in terms of enrollment rates or completion rates (as stated in MDGs); therefore, the functional form is then expanded by replacing Edu (outcomes) by Gross Enrollment Rates of primary (GERp) being a function of several other explanatory variables including Population of ages 0-14 (PoP), Number of Primary Schools (NPS), Pupil-Teacher Ratio (PTR), Government Spending in education (GSE) and Literacy Rate (Lit) because these variables are closely associated with educational outcomes. The ForAID is replaced by Official Development Assistance (ODA). So, the new equation becomes:

$$\mathbf{GERp = f (ODA, PoP, NPS, PTR, GSE, Lit, CorpI)\dots\dots (ii)}$$

It can be expressed in form of a mathematical equation as follows:

$$\mathbf{Y_t = f(X_{1t}, X_{2t}, X_{3t}, X_{4t}, X_{5t}, X_{6t}, X_{7t})}$$

The same equation is then converted into econometric model for the purpose of estimation and analysis:

$$\mathbf{Y_t = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 X_{1t} + \alpha_2 X_{2t} + \alpha_3 X_{3t} + \alpha_4 X_{4t} + \alpha_5 X_{5t} + \alpha_6 X_{6t} + \alpha_7 X_{7t} + e_{1t}}$$

Where:

- Y_t GERp = Gross Enrollment Rate of primary
- X_{1t} ODA= Official Development Assistance
- X_{2t} PoP = Population aged 0-14 as percentage of population
- X_{3t} NPS = Number of Primary Schools
- X_{4t} PTR = Pupil-Teacher Ratio in Primary Schools
- X_{5t} GSE = Government Spending in Education
- X_{6t} Lit = Literacy Rate
- X_{7t} CorpI = Corruption Indices

e_{1t}
t = 1, 2, 3,.....

This functional equation can also be shown in form of circular diagrammatic model as below:

Figure No. 1: Circular diagrammatic model

3.2 Data Collection

The study uses Time Series Data for the period 1995 to 2012. Data is obtained from secondary data sources including various issues of Economic Survey of Pakistan, OECD's Creditors' Reporting System, and World Development Indicators (WDI) on the databank of World Bank and Transparency International.

3.3 Data Analysis

For analysis purposes, this study applied three step methodology viz. checking for stationary, checking for autocorrelation and finally applying Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) for estimation. Moreover, descriptive statistics is used to discuss the impacts of corruption on education sector and the status of education in Pakistan.

3.3.1 Stationary Test

When dealing with time series data, the first step is to check the stationary status of the variables involved in the data set. Because the regression of time series data is implied with the assumption that data is stationary this means that the mean and variance of data is constant. In most the practical empirical research, however, the time series data is non-stationary (only weak stationary). In this study, the stationary of the data has been checked using Stochastic Stationary approach.

3.3.2 Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF)

ADF unit root test is used to check the stationary of various explanatory variables which are in our interest are collected. For getting lag selection at large Schwarz Information Criterion is used. If variables are non-stationary at level then we accept null hypothesis.

3.3.3 Autocorrelation

One of the assumptions of OLS is that there should not be any autocorrelation in the data; to satisfy this condition, the autocorrelation in data sample was checked using Durbin-Watson Test.

3.3.4 Multiple Regressions

After checking the stationary status and the autocorrelation, the last step implied was to run multiple regressions on the data under Ordinary Least Squares (OLS).

4.0 Empirical Results and Findings

4.1 Empirical Results:

The results obtained are presented below:

4.1.1 Stationarity Test:

Table 4.1 Results of ADF Test at level

ADF(Augmented Dickey-Fuller) Unit Root test		
Test at level		
Variables	T statistic	Probability
GERp	-0.749060	0.8079
ODA	-1.349123	0.5815
PoP	0.985038	0.9939
NPS	-3.701782	0.0952
PTR	-1.420524	0.5460
GSE	-2.629893	0.7196
Corp	- 1.041675	0.9131

Researcher assumed the null hypothesis that all variables have a unit root (which means that all variables are non-stationary) at level. As a rule, this null hypothesis can be rejected if the p value of a variable is less than or equal to 0.05. The results of ADF test at level as presented in table 4.1 show that all variables are statistically insignificant since the p value of all variables is greater than 0.05. Therefore, we cannot reject the null hypothesis. Hence, all variables in ADF test at level are statistically insignificant and are non-stationary at level. If variables are non-stationary at level, we use differencing to make them stationary. So, here we tested the variables at their 1st difference in order to check if they are stationary or non-stationary at 1st difference. Once again we assumed the null hypothesis that all variables are non-stationary at 1st difference. The results of ADF test at 1st difference are presented in table 4.2.

Table 4.2 ADF Results at 1st Difference

ADF(Augmented Dickey-Fuller) Unit Root test		
Test at 1st Difference		
Variables	T statistic	Probability
GERp	-4.844042	0.0027
ODA	-4.357883	0.0048
PoP	-7.890701	0.0000
NPS	-3.032910	0.0531
PTR	-6.520666	0.0001
GSE	-3.820139	0.0516
Corp	-4.158778	0.0452

We follow the same decision criteria. As illustrated in the results of ADF test at 1st difference in table 4.2; all variables become statistically significant at 1st difference as p value of all variables is less than and/or equal to 0.05. Therefore, we can reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypothesis. Hence, on the basis of these results, we can say that all variables become statistically significant and stationary at their 1st difference. According to the given results, all variables are stationary at their first difference.

4.2 Ordinary Least Squares Method

After fulfilling the requirement of checking stationarity of all variables, the analysis was preceded by applying multiple regressions on the data sample under Ordinary Least Squares method in order to get long-run estimations. The results of which are presented below:

Table 4.3 Results of the OLS Estimation

Variables	Coefficients	t-Statistic	Probability
C	70.13681	2.513821	0.0307
ODA	0.000380	0.396930	0.6998
PoP	-1.905247	-4.129518	0.0020
NPS	0.248020	1.861812	0.0522
PTR	1.130966	2.406041	0.0319
GSE	1.638973	1.487578	0.1677
CORP	-0.057014	-0.670006	0.0510
ODA*COR	-1.932588	-0.814943	0.0430
R-squared	0.798102		
Adj. R-squared	0.780962		
F-statistic	138.4077		
Prob(F-statistics)	0.00000		
D- Watson	2.265627		

The results displayed in table 4.3 show the long run effect of all variables that are independent on Gross Enrolment Rate at the primary school level (GERp) in

Pakistan. The T statistics for all the variables is less than 2 except for PTR. Official development assistance (ODA) is one of the major determinants, which has positive but insignificant effect on Gross enrolment rate of students at the primary school (GERp) in long run. The t-statistic for ODA is less than 2 but the p value is greater than 0.05. Hence, alternative hypothesis (H_1) is not supported. With one unit rise in ODA on average according to results the GERp increases by 0.000380 units. The figures below show the individual trends of dependent variable Gross Enrollment Rates of primary education (GERp) and the independent variable Official Development Assistance (ODA).

Figure 4.1 Individual trend of GERp

Figure 4.2 Individual trend of ODA

As expected, the coefficient of population (PoP) carries negative sign and its impact on GERp is significant. As of results, one unit rise in population decreases GERp by 1.905247 units whereas the p value is 0.002 which is less than 0.05. Therefore, alternative hypothesis H_2 is supported. Increase in population decreases GERp because when there is increase in population, we need more resources to provide education facility to the increasing population. As stated in Pakistan’s Economic Survey, 2013-14, with a projected population of 188 millions, Pakistan stands as the 6th most populous country in the world. The size of population in Pakistan has been on an increasing trend –and a prominent 35-40% of its population has been in the age group of 0-14 years (primary school going children). However, from the fact that government spending in education in Pakistan has always been low –the infrastructure of education system does not improve and increase at the same rate as the increase in population. Therefore, the continuous increase in population means an increase in the school going children also –but we have to either adjust them in the present infrastructure or due to limited facilities at school i.e. limited class rooms, small size of class rooms,

furniture and limited learning materials – a section of eligible school going children remains deprived of availing the education facility. Moreover, due to inflation and poverty, the parents are unable to get their children enrolled for education keeping in view their limited sources of earning in which they have to manage the basic needs of survival. In such situation, provision of education for their children seems a rather luxury—which ultimately remains a lesser priority; hence, affects the enrollment rates.

Figure 4.3 Individual trend of Population (ages 0-14)

Number of Primary Schools (NPS) has positive and significant impact on GERp. On average one unit rise in number of primary schools according to the results, it increases the GERp by 0.24 units. The p value for NPS is 0.05 therefore, alternative hypothesis H_3 is supported. However, the fact is that not much resources and attention is drawn on enhancing and improving the physical infrastructure. Looking at its significant relationship with GERp, it is argued that if given more attention and directed more funds on constructing more primary schools, this may in turn bring significant impact on GERp because more and better schools means increased opportunities available to parents to get their children enrolled.

Figure 4.4 The trend in NPS

Pupil-Teacher Ratio (PTR) has positive and significant impact on GERp, on average one unit rise in pupil-teacher ratio according to the results; it increases the GERp by 1.130966 units whereas the p value is 0.03 which is less than 0.05. So, the alternative hypothesis H_4 is supported. The results for PTR show that there is positive impact of PTR on GERp; moreover, it is quite significant. This means

that less crowded classes are a kind of motivation/encouragement for the parents to send their children in such schools. That is because all the children will avail better learning facility if there is less number of pupils' less than one teacher contrary to the crowded classes –where teacher would not be able to pay sufficient attention to each pupil. Also, the pupils might not get equal access to the learning materials and they may face seating problems due to limited furniture.

Figure 4.5: The trend in Pupil-Teacher Ratio

The variable of government spending in education (GSE) is showing positive impact on GERp though insignificant. According to results, one unit rise in Government spending on education improves the GERp by 1.638973 units but the value is 0.16 which is greater than 0.05. Therefore, alternative hypothesis H_5 is not supported. The positive impact of GSE on GERp implies the important role of government spending in education sector. However, the impact being insignificant draws from the fact that there has been low spending in education by government of Pakistan. On average, the government spending in education has been only two percentage (Sattar). Despite various commitments in the important policy documents of Pakistan, the government has not been able to trigger it as per planned commitments. There is a dire need of increasing government spending in education because its practical impact on GERp is prominent and can help increase it.

Figure: 4.6 Trend of Government Spending in education

Corruption as expected has negative sign to its coefficient but it has significant effect on GERp results support the findings of Abdiweli & Isse, 2003. The t-statistic for CorPI is less than 2 whereas the p value is less than 0.05. So, the

alternate hypothesis (H_6) can be accepted. One unit raise in corruption on average according to the results it decreases the GERp by -0.057014 units. The figure below shows the individual trend of independent variable corruption.

Figure 4.7 Individual trend of Corruption

Since, the main object of this research is to see the impact of official development assistance in the presence of corruption ($ODA*COR$) on gross enrollment rate of students at primary school; we ran the OLS regression also with $ODA*COR$ as interactive variables.

The results further show that there is negative and significant impact of official development assistance in the presence of corruption on gross enrollment rate of students at primary level of education. One unit rise in $ODA*COR$ declines the GERp by -1.932588 units and the p value is 0.04 which is below 0.05. On the basis of this result, we can accept the alternative hypothesis (H_7).

The value of 0.798102 for R-squared and 0.780962 for adjusted R-squared, defines the model as a good fit on whole. While probability (p) values define the significance of each variable individually; the f-statistic values define the significance of overall model. In case of this study, the f-statistic value of 138.4 with Prob (f-statistic) 0.00000 shows that the model as a whole is significant. The value of Durbin-Watson test may lie between 0 and 4. A Durbin-Watson test value of more than 2 confirms that there is no autocorrelation in the data. For this study, the Durbin-Watson test value is 2.265627, which confirms that there is no autocorrelation problem within the data.

Moving on to the qualitative part of this study, the facts related to the state of primary education in Sindh provinces are presented below:

The Sindh education department has been going through various problems like that of ghost teachers, dummy schools, feudal intervention and others. The Government has been offering various incentives including free of cost text books, fee waiver and payment of monthly stipend in order to encourage the participation in education.

In order to draw an idea of the performance of Sindh education department with regards to MDGs target, the facts relating to primary education in Sindh are presented in Table 4.4 below which are then presented graphically in Figure 4.8

Table 4.4 GER progress of Sindh province against MDGs' target

Year	MDGs target	GER
2005	100	75
2006	100	80
2007	100	79
2008	100	80
2009	100	84
2010	100	84
2011	100	84
2012	100	79

Source: Economic Survey of Pakistan

Figure 4.8 GER progress of Sindh against MDGs' target

Table 4.5 Literacy Rate progress of Sindh against MDGs' target

Year	MDGs target	Literacy Rate
2005	88	56
2006	88	55
2007	88	55
2008	88	56
2009	88	59
2010	88	58
2011	88	59
2012	88	60

Source: Economic Survey of Pakistan

Figure 4.9 Literacy Rate progress of Sindh against MDGs' target

Table 4.6 NER performance of Sindh against MDGs' target

Year	MDGs target	NER
2005	100	48
2006	100	50
2007	100	50
2008	100	51
2009	100	54
2010	100	54
2011	100	53
2012	100	50

Source: Economic Survey of Pakistan

Figure 4.10 NER progress of Sindh against MDGs' target

The figures relating to the three measuring indicators of MDGs pertaining to Sindh are presented in Table 4.7 and Figure 4.11 below; in order to see how the provincial progress towards UPE has been like.

Table 4.7 GER, NER and Literacy Rate progress of Sindh

Year	GER	NER	Literacy Rate
2005	75	48	56
2006	80	50	55
2007	79	50	55
2008	80	51	56
2009	84	54	59
2010	84	54	58
2011	84	53	59
2012	79	50	60

Source: Economic Survey of Pakistan

Figure 4.11 GER, NER and Literacy Rate progress of Sindh

Another aspect of Sindh’s educational performance is presented as a comparison of various indicators with that of the national performance and other provinces’ performance

Figure 4.12 Literacy Rate comparison of Sindh with National and Provincial Literacy Rate

Source: Economic Survey of Pakistan

From this figure, we can see that the Literacy rate performance of Sindh is satisfactory in comparison to national and provincial literacy rates.

In the next figure, the performance of Sindh in Gross Enrollment Rate (GER) is compared with the GER at national level and GER of other provinces.

Figure 4.13 GER comparison of Sindh with National and Provincial GER

Source: Economic Survey of Pakistan

As depicted in figure 4.13, the GER performance of Sindh is lower than the National GER. Sindh also lags behind Punjab and Khyber Pakhtoon khwa (KPK) in GER whereas it has better GER in comparison to Balochistan. Figure 4.14 compares the Net Enrollment Rate (NER) of Sindh with that of National NER and NER of other provinces.

Figure 4.14 NER comparison of Sindh with National and Provincial NER

Source: Economic Survey of Pakistan

NER shows mixed performance of Sindh. The NER of Sindh is lower than national NER as well as that of Punjab; whereas Sindh has better NER performance in comparison to KPK and Baluchistan.

4.3 Findings

The main agenda here is to analyze the relationship between how foreign aid affects gross enrolment rate of students at the primary schools when the corruption is controlled for. For this purpose we have applied Ordinary Least Squares method on the time series data spanning from 1995 to 2012. The control variables included are youth dependency aging 0-14, number of primary schools, pupil-teachers ratio in the primary schools, government spending in education and the literacy rate. We examined the impact of Official Development Assistance (ODA –a sub-category of Foreign Aid) on the Gross Enrollment Rates of primary education (GERp) in Pakistan.

As a starting point, the stationarity status of variables was checked using Augmented Dickey Fuller (ADF) test, the results of which show that all data series are non-stationary at level whereas after applying differencing, the time series become stationary at its 1st difference. Thereof, OLS for estimation was applied. After running regressions on the data, the estimated coefficient suggests a positive association between ODA and gross enrolment rate of students at the primary schools; however, the coefficients are small and insignificant. The result supports findings of Michaelowa & Weber (2007), Michaelowa (2004), and Kassandra & Michaelowa (2013). The result also supports the findings of Anwar & Aman (2010); Anwar & Khalid (2011) to the extent that there is positive impact of aid on the educational outcomes. However, in their studies, they have concluded significant effect of aid on educational outcomes. The difference in findings may be because of various reasons like due to the difference of variables, time period, data sources, methods (techniques) used in their studies.

The value of R-squared (0.798102) and adjusted R-squared (0.780962) is high which defines the model as a good fit on whole. Then, Official Development Assistance and corruption perception variables are used as interactive variables. It is done since interaction of variables not only greatly expands the understanding about the variables in the model but also helps understanding how one variable will behave in the presence of another. Like here, we hypothesize to estimate the effect of foreign aid, measured by official development assistance on gross enrolment rate of students at the primary schools in presence of corruption.

There is positive but insignificant relationship between foreign aid and gross enrolment rate of students at the primary schools as is suggested by the estimated coefficient. However, once we interact the variable of corruption with foreign aid the interactive estimated coefficient is negative and significant with p value being less than 0.05. This implies that when foreign aid is corrupted, it negatively affects gross enrolment rate of students at the primary schools.

5.0 Conclusion & Policy Implications

5.1 Conclusion

The main objective of this study is to analyze the impact of foreign aid on primary education amid corruption in Pakistan. Using time series data for the period 1995-2012; the study focused in particular on Target-2A of Goal-2 of the Millennium Development Goals (MDGs). As suggested by previous studies, the role of foreign aid in growth and development of a country is quite positive and important. However, some of its negative impressions have also been witnessed which include increased dependency on aid and corruption. Though, researchers have found a positive relationship between foreign aid and growth, however, they also associated it with the conditions of good governance and good policy making. The empirical results of this study show positive impact of ODA on educational outcomes in country. However, when corruption is interacted with foreign aid, the impact comes out to be negative. To be more specific, the Gross Enrollment Rates in primary education (GERp) increase due to foreign aid; however, when there is corruption in country, the results are affected as GERp then decreases. Corruption is like an epidemic disease for every sector of an economy. In particular, when a sector is of such high importance and plays vital role in human capital, social stability and economic development, is prone to be getting affected of the disastrous disease, we need to be extra cautious and attentive. We need to take all possible measures and ensure to save ourselves, the country and the future of younger generations from its effects. As in human body, brain is the most important part, so is education among all other sectors because it is through education that we can make rapid, enormous and sustainable development in all other sectors.

Education serves manifold purposes related to personal, social and economic motives but the presence of corruption deteriorates the main purpose of education. The quality of education suffers a great deal due to corrupt practices in the education system. The most damaging role of corruption in education is that the younger generation remains deprived of getting proper knowledge and skills and if the younger generation lacks such learning; they would ultimately not be able to contribute in the national activities of productive nature. Moreover, being part of such corrupt practices the students accept these practices without any odds. Thus, corruption gets infused in the young generation as a norm. The inclusion of smaller administrative levels in education opens doors for more corruption in education. Corruption also triggers when there is political intervention in appointments, promotions and transfers of teachers, opening of schools, providing funds for provision of basic facilities in the schools. In case of splitting more administrative units, the corruption takes place in form of bribes, misuse of schools for personal and commercial purposes, sale of educational materials and books which were meant to be freely distributed, fake receipts and payments on account of goods purchased for use in schools.

Government spending (budget allocation) also suffers of corruption be it of small magnitude or the large one. Less proportion of education budget is often associated with high levels of corruption. The funds and resources may be embezzled by the authorities concerned and also there may be the non-monetary corruption in form of giving undue favours and nepotism.

In order to curb corruption, there is need for transparency, continuous evaluation and monitoring on government's part whereas parents, teachers and students alike need to play their role in making a difference. However, as a social practice, the rope pulling needs to start from the high-ups.

5.2 Policy Implications

- Government should work on governance related issues, that is to concentrate on formulating more effective policies
- It is an accepted belief that formation of policies is easier than execution of policies, government should pay special attention on implication of policies for them to be more effective
- Monitoring and evaluation processes should be made robust and continual, so that the discrepancies that occur may be addressed timely and in a better way. Thus, flaws may be fixed
- Though, the problem may be of national level but every individual section of the country and the administrative unit is an equal player and contributor. Each of them can play their role in ensuring success at the national level, therefore, each one of them be treated equally in policy making, execution, monitoring, resource allocation and every step of the like nature that matters in the overall result

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